

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-205-IG-10% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	117	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	0
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/8/2022 3:52:10 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 9:29:59 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	4.198	976724	50.43	155626
2	4.732	959929	49.57	137444

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-202-IG-10% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	16	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	1
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	7.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/8/2022 4:11:02 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 9:31:27 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	4.202	5789791	99.35	908887
2	4.757	37632	0.65	4642